

DEVELOPMENT OF A MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF AN AERONAUTICAL INFORMATION SERVICE SYSTEM WITH RELATIVE AND ABSOLUTE PRIORITIES IN A TELECOMMUNICATION NETWORK

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Abstract. *This study presents the development of a mathematical model for an Aeronautical Information Service (AIS) system within a telecommunication network, focusing on the implementation of relative and absolute priorities to optimize data transmission and service reliability.*

Keywords: *aeronautical Information Service, mathematical modeling, telecommunication network, priority systems, data transmission, service reliability, optimization.*

According to the discipline of telecommunication network maintenance, there are priority and non-priority maintenance disciplines. In networks with non-priority maintenance, incoming data is processed in the order of their receipt, i.e. the importance or urgency of the message is not taken into account. In networks with priority maintenance, the importance or urgency of the message is taken into account when processing incoming data. That is, some incoming data may have a certain priority over others when processed.

The tasks of managing aeronautical information in a telecommunication network by complex technical complexes in real time usually require the use of multi-machine or multi-processor systems [1]. This is done for reasons of increasing the productivity of technical complexes in the air navigation system, as well as taking into account the requirements for the reliability and organization of their technical maintenance. Differences in the importance of tasks, their labor intensity and requirements for the efficiency of the solution lead to the introduction of priority maintenance disciplines [2] in the air navigation system.

To calculate the probability-time characteristics of information flows in the air navigation system, the Laplace-Stieltjes transform (LST) and the Mk/Gk/N/ type Queuing system (QS) model (exponential law of receipt of requests, random law of servicing requests in a mass service system with N devices and an infinite queue) with a relative priority of servicing aeronautical information flows were used. In [3], formulas are proposed for calculating the average waiting time for the start of servicing information flows for the first two moments for the Mk/Gk/N/ type QS in an N-channel system with relative priority:

$$\omega_{j,1} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i b_{i,2}}{2(1-R_{j-1})(1-R_j)}, \quad j = \overline{1, k}, \quad (1)$$

$$\omega_{j,2} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i b_{i,3}}{3(1-R_{j-1})(1-R_j)} + \frac{\left(\sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_i b_{i,2}\right)\left(\sum_{i=1}^j \lambda_i b_{i,2}\right)}{2(1-R_{j-1})^2(1-R_j)^2} + \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda b_{i,2i}\right)\left(\sum_{i=1}^{j-1} \lambda i,2\right)}{2(1-R_{j-1})^3(1-R_j)}, \quad (2)$$

where: $R_j = \sum_{i=1}^j \lambda_i b_{i,2}$ – coefficient of system loading with packets up to the j -th type;

$w_{j,1}$ – first moment of average packet waiting time;

$w_{j,2}$ – second moment of average packet waiting time;

λ_i – intensity of arrival of the i -th flow;

b_i – initial moments of distribution of service duration of the i -th flow;

k – number of priorities in the system.

Expressions (1) and (2) determine the first and second moments of the average packet waiting time in the Mk/Gk/N/ type QS system with relative priority in a single-channel communication system [4]. The proposed method allows calculating priority systems with arbitrary and different service time distributions for single-channel aeronautical information service systems.

Due to the fact that, as is known, heterogeneous information flows circulate in the telecommunication network (TN), for servicing this type of traffic there is a need to obtain a mathematical model of a priority telecommunication network based on the model of the Mk/Gk/N/ type QS with relative priority in the case of priorities with an unreliable servicing device [5]. In systems with relative priorities, an active thread is executed until it leaves the processor (node) by itself, going into a waiting state, or if an error occurs, or the thread terminates.

According to and by additivity, the random delivery time of a packet with the k -th priority will be determined as

$$t_{dk} = t_{wk} + t_{hk}, k = \overline{1, P}, \quad (3)$$

and the distribution function (DF) of the packet's residence time

$$V_k(t) = W_k(t) * H_k(t), \quad (4)$$

where $*$ is the Stieltievs convolution.

From expression (4) we obtain the average time of stay of a packet of the k -th priority in the transmission link

$$T_k = \int_0^{\infty} t \cdot dV_k(t), \quad (5)$$

To find the service time of packets of the k -th priority in the transmission link, we use the LST with the DF of the service time of packets of the k -th priority at time t . According to [5]:

$$Q_k(\nu) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\nu t} dV_k(t) = w_k(\nu) \cdot h_k(\nu), \quad (6)$$

where ν is the intensity of information aging, $\nu = 1/T_z$;

T_z – the average aging time;

$w_k(t)$ - LST from DF $W_k(t)$ is the waiting time for the start of servicing packets of the k -th priority at time t ;

$h_k(t)$ – LST from DF $H_k(t)$ is service time of packets of the k -th priority at the moment of time t .

Formalizing the process of transmission in the TN using the Mk/Gk/N/ type QS with relative priority, we obtain an expression for the LST from the DF of the waiting time for the start of servicing the k -th priority [5]:

$$w_k(v) = \left\{ \frac{1 - \sum_{i=1}^p \rho_i}{\sigma \varphi_1 + e(\sigma)[1 - \sigma(\varphi_1)]} \left[\frac{e(\sigma)(v + \sigma_{k-1}(1 - h_{k-1}(v))) + \sigma(1 - e(\sigma))}{[1 - \varphi(v + \sigma_{k-1}(1 - h_{k-1}(v)))]} \right] + \sum_{i=k+1}^p \lambda_i [1 - B_i(v + \sigma_{k-1}(1 - h_{k-1}(v)))] \right\} / v - \lambda_k B_k(v + \sigma_{k-1}(1 - h_{k-1}(v))), \quad (7)$$

$$h_0(v) = \sigma_0 = 0; \quad \sigma = \sum_{i=1}^p \lambda_i; \quad \sigma_{j-1} = \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} \lambda_i.$$

Now we will give a formula for calculating the average waiting time of the j -th packet with absolute priority in the Mk/Gk/N/ ∞ type QS system and additional servicing of unserved information flows in the air navigation system

$$\omega_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^j \lambda_i b_{i,2}}{2(1 - R_{j-1})(1 - R_j)} + \frac{b_{j,1}}{1 - R_{j-1}}, \quad j = \overline{1, k}, \quad (8)$$

$$R_j = \sum_{i=1}^j \lambda_i b_{i,2} \quad \text{– system load factor for requests up to type } j;$$

λ_i – intensity of arrival of the i -th flow;

b_i – initial moments of distribution of service duration of the i -th flow.

With absolute priority, priority flows with intensities arrive at the input of the Mk/Gk/N/ ∞ type QS. Packets with smaller numbers have absolute priority over packets with larger numbers. Using the mathematical apparatus of the Laplace Stieltjes transform (LST), we find the DF of the waiting time for the start of servicing the k -th priority:

$$w_k(v) = \frac{1 - \sum_{i=1}^p \rho_i}{\sigma \varphi_1 + e(\sigma)[1 - \sigma(\varphi_1)]} \cdot \frac{\left[e(\sigma)(v + \sigma_{k-1}(1 - h_{k-1}(v))) + \sigma(1 - e(\sigma))[1 - \varphi(G)] \right]}{v - \lambda_k B_k(v + \sigma_{k-1}(1 - h_{k-1}(v)))}, \quad (9)$$

$$G = v + \sigma_{k-1}(1 - h_{k-1}(v)).$$

Taking into account (9) the average delay time of a packet with absolute priority (re-servicing) for the k -th priority is determined by the formula:

$$T_k = w_{1k} + h_{1k} + V_k, \quad k = \overline{1, P}, \quad (10)$$

V_k – mean time of service interruption

$$V_k = \frac{\sigma_{k-1}}{1 - \sigma_{k-1}} \cdot h_{1,k-1} \quad \sigma_{k-1} = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \lambda_i$$

where $h_{1,k-1}$ - corresponds to the expression.

Unlike the relative priority, formula (10) is supplemented by a third term – the average interruption time, representing the time losses associated with the interruption of low-priority packet service with the arrival of high-priority packets. The performance characteristics of telecommunication networks largely depend on the probability of timely delivery of aeronautical information to the network, where the priority of incoming information flows and its ability to timely adapt to changing operating conditions play an important role.

Taking into account (8), the probability of timely delivery of a packet of the k -th priority, taking into account reliability, absolute priority and servicing of newly lost packets for a QS of the type $\overline{M}_k/\overline{G}_k/\overline{N}/\infty$:

$$Q_k(v) = \frac{1 - \sum_{i=1}^{\rho} \rho_i}{\sigma\varphi_1 + e(\sigma)[1 - \sigma\varphi_1]} \left[\frac{e(\sigma) \cdot (G) + \sigma(1 - e(\sigma))(1 - \varphi G)}{v - \lambda_k + \lambda_k B_k(G)} \right] \cdot h_{k-1}(v), \quad (11)$$

$$G = v + \sigma_{k-1}(1 - h_{k-1}(v)); \quad \varphi_1 = \frac{1}{d}; \quad e(\sigma) = \frac{c}{\sigma + c}; \quad \varphi(v) = \frac{d}{d + v}.$$

The average packet delivery time for a multi-level network T is calculated "along different routes relative to the share of the flow passing through them. Based on two possible methods of establishing a path (virtual channel) for a multi-level structure through nodes of the r -th stage and a subnet of the r -th stage, the overall network delivery time can be represented as":

$$[6] \quad T = \frac{1}{\Lambda} \sum_{r=2}^R [2(\lambda_{r-1,r} m_{r-1,r} T_{r-1,r}) + 2(\lambda_{r,r} m_{r,r} T_{r,r}) + (\lambda_r n_r T_r)] \quad , \quad (12)$$

Λ - total intensity of the flow entering the network;

R - number of hierarchy stages;

λ - intensity of incoming information flows;

n_r - number of switching nodes at the r -th stage;

m_r - number of communication channels at the r -th stage;

$m_{r-1,r}$ - number of communication channels in the inter-level subnet with index $(r-1,r)$

The developed mathematical models [7] of priority servicing of information flows can be used in the problems of calculating the probability-time characteristics of a telecom network, comparing various priority service disciplines in air navigation information flows, monitoring operators in the air navigation system and for calculating the economic efficiency of a multi-agent monitoring system, etc. Determining the economic efficiency of a multi-agent monitoring system using the Laplace-Stieltjes mathematical apparatus is possible through channel load balancing and increasing the system's efficiency. The proposed formula for calculating the economic efficiency coefficient (EE) is as follows:

$$EE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (W_i * P_i)}{C_{maint} + C_{energy} + C_{failure}} \quad (13)$$

W_i — weight of priority channel i ;

P_i — the probability of successful data transmission through channel i , calculated using Laplace-Stieltjes:

$$P_i = 1 - \int_0^t L_s(x) dx \quad (14)$$

$L_s(x)$ — channel load distribution function;

C_{maint} — network maintenance costs;

C_{energy} — energy consumption costs;

C_{failure} — system failure troubleshooting costs.

Improving the priority information service system: Using the Laplace-Stieltjes apparatus allows for uniform distribution of the load between channels, minimizing the risk of overloads. This leads to a reduction in the delay time of data transmission.

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